

Blockchain Technology and Applications

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Abstract

1. Introduction

Henry Wang created IBAF and UCCO to promote global Blockchain technology and applications; and serves as adviser to several Blockchain associations to enhance International cooperation. After receiving his master's degree in Physics from Peking University in 1999, Wang obtained a full scholarship for a Doctorate of Astronomy and Physics degree at Northwestern University in the United States. In 2000, Wang Qiheng transferred to Washington University in St. Louis to pursue a Doctoral degree in Computer Science. During his doctoral studies, Mr. Wang served as a core development member and director of business development for Erlang Technology in the United States. In 2006, Henry Wang left school and worked on several business, leading to the formation of the SmartMesh Foundation in Singapore, to realize his dream of the exchange of information and value without boundaries (Internet of Value). In April, 2018, Silicon valley IT magazine APAC CIO Outlook named SmartMesh among the world's top 10 blockchain technology solution providers for 2018. Henry Wang is a Thought Leader in the global Blockchain field and a world renowned technical expert. His research and development projects cover Internet Protocol, Blockchain, Chip design, Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Edge Computing, Internet of Things, and Internet of Everything

Author biography

Henry Wang Henry Wang's mission is to build a complete Internet of Value ecosystem using SmartMesh's peer-to-peer connectivity applications between smart phones and smart devices. An interplanetary, distributed and self-organized mobile mesh network is being constructed by SmartMesh to support a wide array of next generation edge computing, edge storage, and edge intelligence applications.

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